

The Influence of Several Variables on Employee Performance Job Satisfaction as a Mediation Variable of the DRM Bank

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Abstract

The purpose of this research was to determine the influence between Completeness of Facilities, Quality of Human Resources and Environmental Conditions on Employee Performance and Job Satisfaction as a Mediating Variable at PT. DRM Thamrin Area. Using a purposive sampling method with a research sample of 55 people. Using quantitative data types by analyzing primary data sources in the form of questionnaire distribution results, data analysis using the Smart PLS program with the SEM-PLS analysis method. The research results show that, 1) Partially there is a significant positive influence on the completeness of facilities, the quality of human resources on employee performance but there is no influence on environmental condition variables; 2) Partially there is a significant positive influence on the completeness of facilities, quality of human resources and environmental conditions on job satisfaction; 3) Partially there is a significant positive influence on the completeness of facilities on employee performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable for employees, but there is no influence on the variables of human resource quality and environmental conditions.

Keywords

Completeness of Facilities, Quality of Human Resources and Environmental Conditions, Employee Performance and Job Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Since the monetary crisis in 1997 which demonstrated weak supervision and regulation of banking in Indonesia, many banks experienced financial difficulties and eventually went bankrupt. The government then carried out banking restructuring and formed the National Banking Restructuring Agency (BPPN) to handle financial problems in the banking sector. One of the banks resulting from this restructuring is PT. DRM was founded in 1998 as a result of the merger of four state-owned banks. PT. DRM is a commercial bank that provides various financial products and services, such as savings, deposits, credit and investments. Apart from that, PT. DRM also has businesses in the insurance, asset management and sharia banking sectors through its subsidiaries. Since its founding, PT. DRM has developed into one of the largest banks in Indonesia. Currently PT. DRM is the largest bank in terms of assets in Indonesia with total assets as of December 2022 reaching IDR 1,992 trillion or growing 15.5% year on year (Ayyi Hidayah, 2022).

PT. DRM continues to increase, where the average every year increases by 12.09%. Not only assets, net profit from PT. DRM was also recorded to be very good, namely IDR 41.2 trillion or growing 46.9% year on year. The growth of company assets and profits can be an indicator of the company's success in managing its business and expanding the reach of services to customers. However, high asset growth does not always mean that employee performance will also increase. Therefore, banks as financial service providers must maintain and maximize the performance of their employees who also act as assets of the company itself.

Employee job satisfaction is a major concern, but around 60% to 70% of the total employees of PT. DRM Thamrin Area is dissatisfied with their working conditions. One of the main factors contributing to this dissatisfaction is the lack of quality human resources in these companies, which is experienced by approximately 35% to 45% of employees. Deficiencies in the capabilities, training and competence of work teams significantly affect the company's performance and ability to achieve strategic goals. Furthermore, around 30% to 40% of employees complain about a lack of attention to working environment conditions, including a lack of maintenance and comfortable settings.

Poor physical conditions, inadequate lighting, and noise can disrupt employee well-being and concentration. Furthermore, around 25% to 35% of employees also feel that incomplete work facilities, such as inadequate equipment and technology, as well as minimal recreation and relaxation facilities, are detrimental to their work experience. This dissatisfaction directly hinders motivation and morale, results in decreased productivity, and even increases the risk of employee turnover. Job satisfaction describes positive feelings about a job, resulting from an evaluation of its characteristics. Someone with a high level of job satisfaction holds positive feelings about their job, while someone with a low level of job satisfaction holds negative feelings (Robbins and Judge, 2018).

Based on the results of the interview above, PT. DRM Area Thamrin must ensure that the growth of company assets can be balanced with developing employee motivation to provide the best performance by providing solutions to the problems described. Thus, employee performance can increase along with the growth of company's total assets, thereby providing long-term benefits for the company.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Performance

An employee's ability to achieve goals and meet the standards set by the organization where they work. Employee performance also includes the level of effectiveness and efficiency in carrying out their duties and responsibilities as well as their contribution to achieving organizational goals (Armstrong & Baron, 2017). In measuring employee performance the author uses the following indicators: 1) Quantity: the amount of work produced by employees in a certain period; 2) Quality: the level of accuracy and quality of work produced by employees; 3) Time: the extent to which employees are able to complete their tasks and responsibilities within the specified time; 4) Cost: the extent to which employees can manage the budget or costs in carrying out their duties and responsibilities; 5) Efficiency: the level of effective and efficient use of resources in carrying out employee duties and responsibilities; 6) Innovation: the ability of employees to develop new ideas or make improvements in their duties and responsibilities; 7) Competence: the extent to which employees have the skills and abilities needed to carry out their duties and responsibilities (Armstrong & Baron, 2017).

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a positive feeling about a person's job which is the result of evaluating his or her characteristics (Robbins and Judge, 2018). In measuring Job Satisfaction, the author uses the following indicators: 1) Colleague; 2) Work in general; 3) The job itself; 4) Wages; 5) Promotional opportunities; 6) Supervision (Robbins and Judge, 2018).

Completeness of Facilities

Facilities are various kinds of equipment used when working as well as in providing services as the main tool or helper when carrying out work, as well as socially for the interests concerned, which are related to the implementation of work or everything that is worn, applied, utilized and liked by the user. In measuring Completeness of Facilities, the author uses the following indicators: 1) Work tool facilities; 2) work equipment facilities; 3) social facilities (Anandita, 2021).

Quality of Human Resources

The quality of human resources is the ability of an employee to carry out the duties and responsibilities given to him by having the educational background, skills and experience to support the duties and responsibilities that will be carried out so that the company is able to compete in the meaning (Atika *et al.*, 2020:357). In measuring Quality of Human Resources, the author uses the following indicators: 1) Intellectual qualities; 2) Education; 3) Understand the field; 4) Ability; 5) Spirit at work; 6) Organizing planning abilities (Atika *et al.*, 2020:358)

Environmental Conditions

The work environment is everything that is around the employee while working, whether physical or non-physical, direct or indirect, which can affect him and his work while working (Sihaloho. 2019). In measuring Environmental Conditions, the author uses the following indicators: Physical work environment and non-physical work environment (Sihaloho, 2019).

Research Design and Variables

Based on this framework of thought, the author will conduct research to find out the relationship between the first independent variable, namely the completeness of work facilities, the second independent variable, namely the quality of human resources and then the third independent variable, which is the condition of the work environment, on employee performance which is the dependent variable and job satisfaction. which is the mediating variable in this research. This research was conducted empirically on a banking company, namely PT. DRM.

Fig. 1 Research Design and Variables

RESEARCH METHOD

This research is descriptive research that utilizes quantitative methods. The sampling technique used in this research is a purposive sampling technique where the characteristics or criteria that will be used to collect samples in this research are employees of PT. DRM Thamrin area who have positions as implementers and officers who have worked for at least 1 year, totaling 55 people. The types of data used are primary and secondary data.

The primary data for this research comes from the results of questionnaires distributed. Meanwhile, secondary data used in research comes from books, scientific journals and online articles. Data analysis uses the Smart PLS approach. Smart Partial Least Square is a variant-based Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) model. Partial Least Square (PLS) is a specific scale analysis method, and the number of samples used is relatively small (Ghozali, 2018). Partial Least Square aims to help researchers to obtain latent variable and linear aggregate values from the indicators. Partial Least Square produces two models, namely Outer Modeling and Inner Modeling (Audirachman, 2022).

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Convergent Validity

Testing convergent validity, the outer loading or loading factor value is used as appeared on Table 1. Then, an indicator is declared to meet convergent validity in the good category if the outer loading value is > 0.7 .

Table 1 Outer Model Convergent Validity

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loadings	Criteria
Completeness of Facilities	KF1	0,882	Valid
	KF2	0,822	Valid
	KF3	0,794	Valid
	KF4	0,910	Valid
	KF5	0,892	Valid
	KF6	0,864	Valid
	KF7	0,845	Valid
	KF8	0,891	Valid
	KF9	0,832	Valid
Quality of Human Resources	KSDM1	0,895	Valid
	KSDM2	0,864	Valid
	KSDM3	0,898	Valid
	KSDM4	0,888	Valid
	KSDM5	0,896	Valid
	KSDM6	0,864	Valid
Environmental Conditions	KL1	0,859	Valid
	KL2	0,892	Valid
	KL3	0,881	Valid
	KL4	0,899	Valid
	KL5	0,927	Valid
	KL6	0,873	Valid
	KL7	0,872	Valid
Employee Performance	KK1	0,870	Valid
	KK2	0,902	Valid
	KK3	0,858	Valid
	KK4	0,879	Valid

	KK5	0,864	Valid
	KK6	0,838	Valid
	KK7	0,877	Valid
Job Satisfaction	KEKE1	0,911	Valid
	KEKE2	0,911	Valid
	KEKE3	0,855	Valid
	KEKE4	0,918	Valid
	KEKE5	0,892	Valid
	KEKE6	0,869	Valid

Source: Author, September 2023

The following are the values for each indicator in the research variables, as in Table 2.

Table 2 Indicator Values for Each Variables

Indicator	Completeness of Facilities	Job Satisfaction	Employee Performance	Environmental Conditions	Quality of Human Resources
KEKE1	0,639	0,911	0,790	0,705	0,700
KEKE2	0,684	0,911	0,755	0,682	0,634
KEKE3	0,618	0,855	0,670	0,683	0,564
KEKE4	0,577	0,918	0,714	0,718	0,651
KEKE5	0,759	0,892	0,819	0,723	0,737
KEKE6	0,601	0,869	0,713	0,544	0,665
KF1	0,882	0,673	0,715	0,653	0,643
KF2	0,822	0,602	0,622	0,564	0,530
KF3	0,794	0,526	0,498	0,414	0,426
KF4	0,910	0,672	0,687	0,615	0,569
KF5	0,892	0,648	0,644	0,569	0,508
KF6	0,864	0,614	0,604	0,480	0,522
KF7	0,845	0,595	0,656	0,466	0,489
KF8	0,891	0,685	0,672	0,619	0,594
KF9	0,832	0,590	0,662	0,492	0,603
KK1	0,577	0,732	0,870	0,719	0,746
KK2	0,682	0,730	0,902	0,680	0,696
KK3	0,681	0,706	0,858	0,606	0,653
KK4	0,693	0,737	0,879	0,700	0,714
KK5	0,638	0,758	0,864	0,730	0,708
KK6	0,662	0,708	0,838	0,687	0,647
KK7	0,624	0,715	0,877	0,649	0,705
KL1	0,529	0,662	0,666	0,859	0,632
KL2	0,655	0,742	0,746	0,892	0,607
KL3	0,493	0,611	0,632	0,881	0,613
KL4	0,579	0,653	0,759	0,899	0,617
KL5	0,558	0,720	0,715	0,927	0,608
KL6	0,565	0,684	0,675	0,873	0,660
KL7	0,544	0,623	0,660	0,872	0,658
KSDM1	0,542	0,689	0,743	0,656	0,895
KSDM2	0,529	0,641	0,660	0,576	0,864
KSDM3	0,621	0,678	0,732	0,626	0,898
KSDM4	0,588	0,680	0,730	0,610	0,888
KSDM5	0,533	0,655	0,730	0,707	0,896
KSDM6	0,552	0,577	0,640	0,572	0,864

Source: Author, September 2023

As the above, it can be seen that based on convergent validity testing, namely outer loadings, all indicators are declared valid. Thus, the indicators used in this research are valid or have met the requirements of the convergent validity test, meaning that the data provided by respondents from PT. DRM Jakarta Thamrin Area in this research is appropriate and can be measured.

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity of the measurement model (outer model) with reflexive indicators is assessed based on the cross loadings of the measurement with the construct. If the correlation of a construct with other measurement items is greater than that of other constructs, this indicates that the latent construct can predict the size of their block to a greater extent than other blocks. The following is the cross loading on the entire construct:

As the above cross loading value shows that there is good discriminant validity because the correlation value of each indicator on the construct has a higher value compared to the correlation value of indicators on other constructs.

Composite Reliability

Composite Reliability is the part used to test the reliability value of indicators on a variable as appeared on table 3. A variable can be declared to meet composite reliability if it has a composite reliability value > 0.6 , Cronbach's alpha above 0.7. The following are the composite reliability values for each variable used in this research:

Table 3 The Composite Reliability Values

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Result
Completeness of Facilities	0,956	0,962	Reliable
Quality of Human Resources	0,949	0,959	Reliable
Environmental Conditions	0,946	0,956	Reliable
Employee Performance	0,954	0,962	Reliable
Job Satisfaction	0,944	0,956	Reliable

Source: Author, September 2023

As the table above, it can be concluded that the Composite Reliability value for all variables in this study is > 0.6 and the Cronbach's Alpha value for all variables also shows > 0.7 . This shows that each variable has met Composite Reliability so that it can be concluded that all variables have high reliability values.

INNER MODEL

Path Coefficient

Path coefficient evaluation is used to show how strong the effect or significance of the relationship between constructs or variables is. The following are the results of the path coefficient evaluation in this research.

As the above, it can be concluded that the largest path coefficient value is shown by the influence of job satisfaction on employee performance of 2.798. Meanwhile, the smallest path coefficient value is shown by the influence of environmental conditions on employee performance of 1.839. Based on the picture, it can be concluded that all variables in this model have path coefficients with positive numbers. This shows that the greater the path coefficient value of an independent variable on the dependent variable, the stronger the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

R-square

Coefficient determination (R-Square) is used to measure how much an endogenous variable is influenced by other variables. The R-Square results are 0.67 and above for endogenous latent variables in the structural model, indicating that the influence of exogenous variables (which influence) on endogenous variables (which are influenced) is included in the good category. Meanwhile, if the result is 0.33 – 0.67 then it is included in the moderate category, and if the result is 0.19 – 0.33 then it is included in the weak category (Chin, 1998). The following are the results of the R-square calculation in this research.

Table 4 R-square Values

Variable	R Square	Criteria
Job Satisfaction (KEKE)	0,714	Baik
Employee Performance (KK)	0,812	Baik

Source: Author, September 2023

The Table 4 above shows that the variables' completeness of facilities, quality of human resources and environmental conditions can explain that the variable job satisfaction has an R-square value of 0.714 or 71.4% where the remaining 28.6% is represented by other variables outside the research model. Furthermore, the variables completeness of facilities, quality of human resources, environmental conditions and job satisfaction can explain that the employee performance variable has an R-square value of 0.812 or 81.2% where the remaining 18.8% is represented by other variables outside the research model.

Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis testing is carried out through data processing using Smart-PLS 4.0 software, namely the values in the output path coefficients are presented on Table 5 as follows:

Table 5 Statistical Hypothesis Testing

Construct	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics	P Values	Statistic conclusion
Completeness of Facilities → Employee Performance	0,201	2,444	0,015	H _{o1} rejected and H _{a1} accepted
Quality of Human Resources → Employee Performance	0,289	2,511	0,012	H _{o2} rejected and H _{a2} accepted
Environmental Conditions → Employee Performance	0,216	1,839	0,066	H _{o3} rejected and H _{a3} accepted
Completeness of Facilities → Job Satisfaction	0,322	2,543	0,011	H _{o4} rejected and H _{a4} accepted
Quality of Human Resources → Job Satisfaction	0,288	2,533	0,011	H _{o5} rejected and H _{a5} accepted
Completeness of Facilities → Job Satisfaction	0,006	2,753	0,006	H _{o6} rejected and H _{a6} accepted
Job Satisfaction → Employee Performance	0,312	2,798	0,005	H _{o7} rejected and H _{a7} accepted
Environmental Conditions → Job Satisfaction → Employee Performance	0,100	2,007	0,045	H _{o8} rejected and H _{a8} accepted
Quality of Human Resources → Job Satisfaction → Employee Performance	0,090	1,765	0,078	H _{o9} rejected and H _{a9} accepted
Completeness of Facilities → Job Satisfaction → Employee Performance	0,110	1,855	0,064	H _{o10} rejected and H _{a10} accepted

Source: Author, September 2023

As the above, it can be seen that the path coefficient result for the original sample (O) variable of completeness of facilities on job satisfaction is 0.322. The variable quality of human resources on job satisfaction is 0.288. The environmental condition variable on job satisfaction performance is 0.351. The variable of completeness of facilities on employee performance is 0.201. The variable quality of human resources on employee performance is 0.289. The environmental condition variable on employee performance is 0.216. The variable job satisfaction on employee performance is 0.312. The variable of completeness of facilities on employee performance through job satisfaction is 0.100. The variable quality of human resources on employee performance through job satisfaction is 0.090. The variable environmental conditions on employee performance through job satisfaction is 0.110. Then it can also be seen those environmental conditions on employee performance, the quality of human resources on employee performance through job satisfaction and environmental conditions on employee performance through job satisfaction show results that do not have a positive effect, while other hypotheses show results that have a positive effect.

The Effect of Completeness of Facilities on Employee Performance

Based on the previous table 5, it can be seen that the variable Completeness of Facilities on Employee Performance shows a t-statistic value of 2.444 > 1.96, with a P-Value of 0.015 > 0.05 and a path coefficient value of 0.201. So, it can be concluded that the completeness of facilities variables has a significant positive effect on the performance of PT employees. PT. DRM Thamrin Area which means H_{a1} is accepted.

The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Ragil *et al.*, 2021; Mulyadi *et al.*, 2022, which shows that complete work facilities have a significant positive impact on employee performance. Completeness of facilities is of course an important element in carrying out company operations because the completeness of facilities provided will make it easier for employees to carry out their duties, because the more complete the facilities in the workplace, the higher employee productivity will be.

The Effect of Human Resource Competency on Employee Performance

Based on the previous table 5, it can be seen that the human resource competency variable on employee performance shows a t-statistic value of 2.511 > 1.96, with a P-Value of 0.012 > 0.05 and a path coefficient value of 0.289. So, it can be concluded that the human resource competency variable has a significant positive effect on the performance of PT employees. PT. DRM Thamrin Area which means H_{a2} is accepted.

The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Ferdy *et al.*, 2018; Audirachman, 2022; Hadi *et al.*, 2022, which shows that there is a significant positive influence on the quality of human resources on employee performance. The quality of human resources is the most important factor in the success of an organization, the higher the quality of human resources, the better the work performance that will be produced and is one of the main factors in the success or decline of an organization or company.

The Effect of Environmental Conditions on Employee Performance

Based on the previous table 5, it can be seen that the environmental condition variable on employee performance shows a t-statistic value of $1.839 < 1.96$, with a P-Value of $0.066 > 0.05$ and a path coefficient value of 0.216. So, it can be concluded that environmental condition variables do not have a significant positive effect on the performance of PT. DRM Thamrin Area which means H_{a3} is rejected.

This is not in line with research conducted by Bella *et al.*, 2022; Zarkasyi *et al.*, 2020; Arianto, 2022; Ende *et al.*, 2021; Siagian *et al.*, 2018, which shows that there is a significant positive influence on environmental conditions on employee performance. However, this research is supported by Wulan (2019) who shows that there is no significant positive influence on environmental conditions on employee performance. However, a conducive work environment will make employees comfortable in carrying out their work and provide maximum results, of course this has a positive impact on the company.

The Effect of Completeness of facilities on Job Satisfaction

Based on the previous table 5, it can be seen that the variable Completeness of facilities on Job Satisfaction shows a t-statistic value of $2.543 > 1.96$, with a P-Value of $0.011 > 0.05$ and a path coefficient value of 0.322. So, it can be concluded that the completeness of facilities variable has a significant positive effect on Job Satisfaction at PT. DRM Jakarta Thamrin Area, which means H_{a4} is accepted.

The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Ainia, 2021; Mulyadi *et al.*, 2022; Kartika, 2021, which shows that work facilities have a significant positive impact on job satisfaction. Completeness of facilities is of course an important element in carrying out company operations, because the Completeness of facilities provided will make it easier for employees to carry out their duties, because the more complete the facilities in the workplace, the higher employee productivity will be. Facilities are those that are used as tools or main aids when carrying out work, as well as socially for the interests concerned, which are related to the implementation of work or everything that is used, applied, utilized and liked by the user. Therefore, the completeness of work facilities has a positive effect on job satisfaction, because the more complete the facilities in the workplace, the more satisfied employees will be with the facilities provided by the company.

The Effect of Human Resource Competency on Job Satisfaction

Based on the previous table 5, it can be seen that the human resource competency variable on job satisfaction shows a t-statistic value of $2.533 > 1.96$, with a P-Value of $0.011 > 0.05$ and a path coefficient value of 0.288. So, it can be concluded that the human resource competency variable has a significant positive effect on PT job satisfaction. PT. DRM Thamrin Area which means H_{a5} is accepted.

The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Ferdy, 2018; Audirachman, 2022; Prasetya, 2018; Hadi *et al.*, 2022, which shows that there is a significant positive influence on the quality of human resources on job satisfaction. The quality of human resources is the most important factor in the success of an organization, the higher the quality of human resources, the better the work performance that will be produced and is one of the main factors in the success or decline of an organization or company. The quality of human resources is the most important factor in the success of an organization, the higher the quality of human resources, the better the work performance that will be produced and is one of the main factors in the success or decline of an organization or company.

The Effect of Environmental Conditions on Job Satisfaction

Based on the previous table 5, it can be seen that the environmental condition variable on job satisfaction shows a t-statistic value of $2.753 > 1.96$, with a P-Value of $0.006 > 0.05$ and a path coefficient value of 0.006. So, it can be concluded that environmental condition variables have a significant positive effect on job satisfaction at PT. DRM Thamrin Area which means H_{a6} is accepted.

This is in line with research conducted by Zarkasyi *et al.*, 2020; Arianto, 2022; Ende *et al.*, 2021; Siagian *et al.*, 2018, which shows that there is a significant positive influence on environmental conditions on job satisfaction. A conducive work environment will make employees comfortable in carrying out their work and provide maximum results, of course this is very positive for the company.

The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

Based on the previous table 5, it can be seen that the job satisfaction variable on employee performance shows a t-statistic value of $2.798 > 1.96$, with a P-Value of $0.005 > 0.05$ and a path coefficient value of 0.312. So, it can be concluded that the job satisfaction variable has a significant positive effect on employee performance at PT. DRM Thamrin Area which means H_{a7} is accepted.

This is in line with research conducted by Ende et al., 2021; Mulyadi *et al.*, 2022; Ainia, 2021; Prasetya, 2018; Audirachman, 2022; Hadi *et al.*, 2022; Zarkasyi *et al.*, 2020; Arianto, 2022; Siagian *et al.*, 2018, which shows that there is a significant positive influence of job satisfaction on employee performance. A conducive work environment will make employees comfortable in carrying out their work and provide maximum results, of course this is very positive for the company. Which then means that the higher the job satisfaction felt by the employee, the more the employee's performance will increase in other work tasks. has been determined according to his position.

The influence of Completeness of facilities on employee performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable

Based on the previous table 5, it can be seen that the variable completeness of facilities on employee performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable shows a t-statistic value of $2.007 > 1.96$, with P-Values of $0.045 > 0.05$ and a path coefficient value of 0.100. So, it can be concluded that the completeness of the facilities variable has a significant positive effect on employee performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable at PT. DRM Jakarta Thamrin Area, which means H_{a8} is accepted.

This is in line with research conducted by Ainia, 2021, which shows that there is a significant positive influence on the completeness of facilities on employee performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable. Work facilities are provided by the company to each employee in an effort to fulfill needs that are useful for improving performance so as to create high employee productivity and job satisfaction. Therefore, the completeness of work facilities has a positive effect on employee performance and job satisfaction, because the more complete the facilities in the workplace, the more satisfied employees will be with the facilities provided by the company.

The Influence of Human Resource Competency on Performance Employees through job satisfaction as a mediating variable

Based on the previous table 5, it can be seen that the human resource competency variable on employee performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable shows a t-statistic value of $1.765 < 1.96$, with P-Values of $0.078 > 0.05$ and a path coefficient value of 0.090. So, it can be concluded that the human resource competency variable does not have a significant positive effect on employee performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable at PT. DRM Thamrin Area which means H_{a9} is rejected.

The results of this research are not in line with research conducted by Audirachman, 2022; Hadi et al., 2022 which shows that there is a significant positive influence on human resource competence on employee performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable. However, the results of this research are supported by research from Prasetya, 2018 which shows that there is no significant positive influence on human resource competence on employee performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable. The quality of human resources is the most important factor in the success of an organization, the higher the quality of human resources, the better the work performance that will be produced and is one of the main factors in the success or decline of an organization or company.

The Influence of Environmental Conditions on Employee Performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable

Based on the previous table 5, it can be seen that environmental condition variables on employee performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable show a t-statistic value of $1.855 < 1.96$, with P-Values of $0.064 > 0.05$ and a path coefficient value of 0.110. So, it can be concluded that environmental condition variables do not have a significant positive effect on employee performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable at PT. DRM Thamrin Area which means H_{a10} is rejected.

The results of this research are not in line with research conducted by Zarkasyi *et al.*, 2020; Ende *et al.*, 2021; Arianto, 2022, which shows that there is a significant positive influence on environmental conditions on employee performance through job satisfaction. as a mediating variable. However, the results of this research are supported by research from Siagian *et al.*, 2018, which shows that there is no significant positive influence on environmental conditions on employee performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable. A conducive work environment will make employees comfortable in carrying out their work and provide maximum results, of course this is very positive for the company.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

This research aims to analyze the influence of the variable's completeness of facilities, quality of human resources, environmental conditions, job satisfaction and employee performance on PT employees. PT. DRM Thamrin Area. The results of the analysis carried out using Smart-PLS 4.0 which uses 10 hypotheses show mixed results. Based on the results of the data processing output that has been carried out and explained in the previous chapter, the following are the conclusions of this research:

- 1) There is a significant positive influence on the completeness of facilities on employee performance for PT. DRM Thamrin Area employees

- 2) There is a significant positive influence on the quality of human resources on employee performance for PT. DRM Thamrin Area employees
- 3) There is no significant positive influence on environmental conditions on employee performance for PT. DRM Thamrin Area employees
- 4) There is a significant positive influence on the completeness of facilities on job satisfaction for PT. DRM Thamrin Area employees.
- 5) There is a significant positive influence on the quality of human resources on job satisfaction for PT. DRM Thamrin Area employees
- 6) There is a significant positive influence on environmental conditions on job satisfaction for PT. DRM Thamrin Area employees
- 7) There is a significant positive influence on job satisfaction on employee performance for PT. DRM Thamrin Area employees
- 8) There is a significant positive influence on the completeness of facilities on employee performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable for PT. DRM Thamrin Area employees
- 9) There is no significant positive influence on the quality of human resources on employee performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable for PT. DRM Thamrin Area employees
- 10) There is no significant positive influence on environmental conditions on employee performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable for PT. DRM Thamrin Area employees

Suggestions

The results of the conclusions in this research are supported by the data obtained so that researchers can provide suggestions for PT. DRM Thamrin Area, here are some suggestions that can be given, such as:

1. For PT. DRM Thamrin Area

For the management of PT. DRM Thamrin Area is expected to pay more attention to the variables studied, namely completeness of facilities, quality of human resources and environmental conditions because of the many complaints from both implementing employees and visiting officials:

a. Completeness of facilities

Almost all employees complain about the slowness of the hardware they use for work. This really hinders their work because, in this era of digitalization, fast hardware and networks are needed to keep up with the large number of customer visits, processing a lot of data and also making time efficient. For this reason, the writing suggests that periodic checks be carried out on all office facilities, both hardware and software, as well as collecting complaints that should be followed up immediately. Because if not, the work of employees will be greatly hampered which will then cause disappointment among customers.

b. Quality of Human Resources

The number of complaints made by several employees about other employees who were felt to lack ethics and sufficient knowledge for the positions they held hampered the continuity of work. Therefore, the author suggests that when recruiting new prospective employees, it should be done as effectively and with as much detail as possible, so that good quality human resources will be attracted which can then make team collaboration smooth and provide the best results.

c. Environmental conditions

All employees who work at PT. DRM Thamrin Area has often complained about environmental conditions that are far from neat and which then interfere with the running or productivity of employees. Apart from that, senior officials from the head office have also given warnings and mandates to immediately improve environmental conditions so that employees can be more comfortable at work. Therefore, the author would like to suggest that it is better to carry out regular checks on the company environment to find deficiencies that cause employee discomfort at work, so that they can be corrected immediately and do not disrupt the company's activities for a long time.

2. For further research

Future researchers are expected to conduct research with variables that have rarely been studied by previous research so that they can produce a new perspective on the world of education.

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